

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF “ADJECTIVE” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. *This article discusses the degrees of morphology in two distinct languages to illustrate how adjectives are used. Eastern and Western linguists view adjectives very differently, even when arranging them side by side to highlight distinctions and similarities. The past is behind us, but you may take control of the present and create it for yourself in the near future. Thus, we have attempted to illustrate some of the similarities and differences between adjectives in the English and Uzbek languages.*

Keywords: *Adjectives, English and Uzbek languages, Similarities, Differences.*

СХОДЫ И РАЗЛИЧИЯ СЛОВ «ПРЕДЛАЖИТЕЛЬНОЕ» В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И
УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *В этой статье обсуждаются степени морфологии в двух разных языках, чтобы проиллюстрировать, как используются прилагательные. Восточные и западные лингвисты рассматривают прилагательные совершенно по-разному, даже когда располагают их рядом, чтобы подчеркнуть различия и сходства. Прошлое осталось позади, но вы можете взять настоящее под контроль и создать его для себя в ближайшем будущем. Таким образом, мы попытались проиллюстрировать некоторые сходства и различия между прилагательными в английском и узбекском языках.*

Ключевые слова: *Прилагательные, Английский и Узбекский языки, Сходства, Различия.*

Introduction: Adjectives plays a crucial role in effective communication in the English age.

It provides the structure and rules necessary for clear and coherent expression. Learning adjective not only improves your writing and speaking skills, but also helps you gain a deeper understanding of the language. But students may have difficulty comparing their mother tongue with a foreign language, in our example with English. In this article, we compare some adjectives categories in English and Uzbek from grammatical and morphological points of view.

The characteristic features of the adjective as a part of speech are as follows:

1. Their lexical-grammatical meaning of attributes or we may say that they express property of things/persons/;

2. From the morphological view point they have the category of degrees of comparison;

3. From the point of view of their combinability they combine with nouns, as it has already been stated above, they express the properties of things. The words that express things we call nouns. It seems to be important to differentiate the combinability of a word with other words and reference of a word of a part of speech to another part of speech. We put this because adjectives modify nouns but they can combine with adverbs, link verbs and the word “one”:

A white horse. The horse is white.

The sun rose red. The sun rose extremely red.

4. The stem-building affixes are: -ful, -less, -ish, -ous, -ive, -ir, un-, -pre-, in-...;

5. Their syntactic functions are: attribute and predicative.

It is important to point out that in the function of an attribute the adjectives are in most cases used in pre-position; in post- position they are very seldom: time immemorial; chance to come.

The category of comparison of adjectives shows the absolute or relative quality of a substance. [5;24]

An adjective is a word that modifies or describes a noun or pronoun. Adjectives can be used to describe the qualities of someone or something independently or in comparison to something else. Examples: Adjectives in a sentence I like old houses. The boy is tall and skinny.[2]

In both English and Uzbek languages the adjective qualifies or modifies a substance:

English	Uzbek
A new book	yangi kitob
A red dress	qizil ko‘ylak
A clever boy	aqli bola

In English and Uzbek the adjective usually forms combinations with:

1. **Nouns:**Eng.: an interesting book, a tall tree,etc.

Uzb.: qiziqarli kitob, baland daraxt etc.

2. **Link-verbs:**Eng.: was strong, was clever, was old

Uzb.: kuchli edi, aqli edi, qari edi

3. **Adverbs:**Eng.: very interesting, very old

Uzb.: juda qiziqarli, juda eski

According to their structure English and Uzbek adjectives may be:

1. **Simple:**

Eng.: red, good, hot, cold, slow

Uzb: qizil, yaxshi, issiq, sovuq, sekin

2. Derivative:

Eng.: passive, talented, social, snowy

Uzb.: noaktiv, talantli, kirishimli, qorli

3. Compound:

Eng.: big-eyed, deaf-mute, eagle-eyed, never-ending

Uzb.: xushbo'y, vatanparvar, uchburchakli, odamsimon

The word enough which shows the quantity of something or state differs in using in both languages:

In Uzbek “**yetarlicha**” comes before adjective.

e.g. *Jin ham yetarlicha ishonch va xotirjamlik bilan:*

- *Salom, - dedi.*[57]

But in English the word “**enough**” comes after adjective.

e.g. *“Well, they’re easy enough, they’re in the student store-cupboard, we can help ourselves.”*[3;165]

In addition, the English conjunction “**no sooner..., than...**” is used to denote simultaneous actions. It is the negative of “as soon as”.

In English: *No sooner had Mrs. Weasley bent over her son than Lupin Grabbed Harry by the upper arm and dragged him.*[4;69]

In Uzbek: *Saroy eshigidan kirar-kirmas misoli cheksizlikka qadar uzangan zinalarga duch keldilar*[140]

Comparing the usage we identified that the construction in Uzbek grammar is different Which used as ‘participle’.

Moreover, the singular form of English and Uzbek nouns is zero morpheme. We add suffix in both languages in order to make a plural form. We also can see some distinctive features of parts of speech in these languages while English have root exchange in forming degrees of adjectives, in Uzbek we have suffix **-lar** which means respect for adults: *Otamlar* and so on. It should be noted that classification of adjective is considered as problematic in the other compared language.

Therefore, there are different approaches in classifying them into groups.

Summary: As a result of my research, I can say that. Morphological units are crucial for learning because they enable students to read texts more readily and provide vocabulary information that allows them to identify words and understand their meanings when they interact with new words or read ones. An adjective is a grammatical component of speech that describes

and alters a noun. Additionally, it describes the noun's size, color, form, origin, condition, character, and other attributes. Due to the two countries' dissimilar geographic environments, there are variations in the grammatical structures of speech, including how adjective words are formed, prefixes and suffixes are added, comparison degrees are formed, and other forms of expression.

Certain adjectives have multiple fields, making it challenging to create compound words based on their basic forms. One characteristic that sets the Uzbek language apart from other comparable languages is its compositional structure. Eventually, a number of commonalities between the two languages' analyses can be identified, including the presence of affixation types and the quantity of derivative words or suffixes that can alter a word's meaning from one portion of speech to another.

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